

Title: Deep Learning with K-Means applied to community detection in networks.

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INTRODUCTION:

Identifying communities or clusters in graphs in network structure, a K-Mean based approach is more suitable for a lower-dimensional data representation that replaced traditional neural networks based auto-encoders in a deep learning pipelines.

AIM:

To create a new processing pipelines for non overlapping community detection in network structure based entirely on K-Means.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

We propose a novel approach to perform Graph Clustering for Network Community Detection that is entirely based on K-Mean to replace eigenvector decomposition step in Spectral Clustering by an multi layer auto-encoder pipeline implemented using only K-Means clustering algorithm in a recursive way.

RESULTS:

Performed a series of experiments to analysis the network data with ground truth communities that results in the more accuracy, ease of computational time complexity & scalability Deep K-Mean comparing it with the implementation of Spectral Clustering.

CONCLUSIONS:

According to the results of this study, it is more easier to implement the algorithm in a distributed, parallel data processing framework, such as Apache Hadoop or Apache Spark, or to implement improved version of K-Means.

KEYWORDS:

Neural Networks; Apache Hadoop or Apache Spark; Spectral Clustering; K-Mean.

BIOGRAPHY:

Beenish Mehar is highly motivated to become a data scientist, has offered scholarship for SAP via CIBA Consulting Pakistan (Pvt) Limited, has attempted 49 related courses via linked In learning, has completed MBA from Karachi University Business School in Banking & Finance & BBA from Karachi University Business School with major subject Finance & Inferential statistics, her articles has been published in institute of Cost & Management Accountancy Pakistan Management Journal under official flagship in Focused section supporting BIG data & predictive analysis. She is serving as an Senior accountant at DP World Karachi.